

Conference Abstract

Haemocyte dynamics during larval development in *Ceratitis capitata* Wiedemann, 1824 (Diptera: Tephritidae)

Ganina Valentinova Lavchieva-Nacheva[‡], Rumyana Kostova[§], Zhenya Ivanova Ilieva[‡],
Trayan B Dimitrov[¶]

[‡] Faculty of Biology at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", Sofia, Bulgaria
[§] Sofia University, Sofia, Bulgaria
[‡] Institute of Soil Science, Agrotechnology and Plant Protection, Sofia, Bulgaria
[¶] Faculty of Biology at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", София, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Ganina Valentinova Lavchieva-Nacheva (ganinanacheva@uni-sofia.bg)

Received: 09 Dec 2025 | Published: 07 Jan 2026

Citation: Lavchieva-Nacheva G, Kostova R, Ilieva Z, Dimitrov T (2026) Haemocyte dynamics during larval development in *Ceratitis capitata* Wiedemann, 1824 (Diptera: Tephritidae). ARPHA Conference Abstracts 9: e181907. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.9.e181907>

Abstract

The Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* Wied. is one of the world's most destructive fruit pests. Sustainable control is difficult due to its polyphagy, invasiveness, high eradication and containment costs, and the development of insecticide resistance (Giunti et al. 2023). Its presence in Bulgaria was first documented by Katinova et al. (2019).

Understanding the species' defence mechanisms is crucial for effective management. As haemocytes play a key role in insect immunity and development, this study examined their composition and dynamics during the larval development of *C. capitata* to support the future development of biological control strategies.

A laboratory population of *C. capitata* from Thessaloniki (Greece) was maintained in a controlled-environment chamber. Synchronized prepupae reared on an artificial diet (Boller 1985) were used. Haemolymph was collected from 100 individuals per larval instar (first, second, third, and prepupal). Haemocyte types were identified morphologically, and their relative proportions were determined by differential counts. Four adjacent fields (0.02 mm² total) formed one sampling unit, and counts were taken at

10 randomly selected locations per slide. Significant differences between haemocyte type proportions among larval stages were assessed using the χ^2 -test and the z-test.

Six distinct haemocyte types were identified in *C. capitata* hemolymph: prohaemocytes, plasmatocytes, granulocytes, oenocytoids, podocytes, and spherulocytes. Haemocyte composition varied significantly across the four larval stages (Chi-square = 2796.12, df = 15, $p < 0.001$). Pairwised z-test showed also significant difference between each haemocyte share during the four larval stages. Prohaemocytes increased steadily from 13% in L1 to 17% in the prepupal stage, indicating active haematopoiesis. Spherulocytes remained rare and relatively stable (1% in L1 to 0.05% in L4), suggesting a maintenance function. Podocytes rose sharply in L3 and L4, reaching 34% of all haemocytes, likely associated with morphogenetic processes. Oenocytoids were consistently low, highest in early stages - 5% in L1 and declining to 1% in L4, consistent with metabolic and detoxification roles. Plasmatocytes and granulocytes peaked in L3 (35% and 33% respectively), corresponding to maximum immune activity, followed by a slight decline in L4. Overall, the haemocyte profile shifted markedly with larval age, reflecting key physiological processes such as immune responses and preparation for metamorphosis.

Keywords

Mediterranean fruit fly, haemolymph, differential blood counting

Presenting author

Ganina Lavchieva-Nacheva

Presented at

International Conference on Natural Sciences and Biotechnology – Kliment's Days 2025

Funding program

This work was supported by the Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science under the National Research Programme "Healthy Foods for a Strong Bio-Economy and Quality of Life" approved by DCM # 577 / 17.08.2018". The authors thank Dr Panagiotis Milonas from Benaki Institute for initial laboratory population *C. capitata*.

Hosting institution

Faculty of Biology of Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Boller EF (1985) *Rhagoletis cerasi* and *Ceratitis capitata*. In: Sing P, Moore RF (Eds) Handbook of Insect Rearing. 2. Elsevier, 9 pp.
- Giunti G, Benelli G, Campolo O, Canale A, Kapranas A, Liedo P, De Meyer M, Nestel D, Ruiu L, Scolari F, Wang X, Papadopoulos N (2023) Biology, ecology and invasiveness of the Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata*: a review. *Entomologia Generalis* 43 (6): 1221-1239. <https://doi.org/10.1127/entomologia/2023/2135>
- Katinova B, Karadjova O, Ilieva Z (2019) New data on *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) from Bulgaria. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 2 <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.2.e46861>